

***Loryma egregialis* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1838), a new species to Hungary and Central Europe (Lepidoptera, Pyralidae)**

Imre Fazekas & Sándor Farkas

Abstract. The first observation of *Loryma egregialis* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1838) in Hungary and Central Europe is reported. The paper presents the diagnosis of the species, along with a photograph of the male genitalia. The biology of the species is analysed in detail, and its geographical distribution is illustrated on a map. We conclude that *Loryma egregialis* is probably an introduced species. Its establishment in continental Hungary requires further investigation.

Keywords. diagnosis, habitat, bionomy, first record, Hungary, Central Europe

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Author's address.

Imre Fazekas | Pannon Institute | 7625 Pécs, Magaslati út 24. | Hungary
E-mail : fazekas@outlook.com | <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4318-3946>
Sándor Farkas | Florisztika Bt. | 2400 Dunaújváros, Kinizsi u. 5. | Hungary
E-mail: florisztika@gmail.com

Introduction

The genus *Loryma* Walker, 1859, has not been documented as having any species present in Central Europe and Hungary. The second author, an amateur entomologist, routinely collects insects in a suburban residential garden near the industrial town of Dunaújváros in central Hungary. On the night of 28–29 August 2024, a specimen of *Loryma egregialis* was attracted by the ultraviolet light emitted by the SMD 5050 LED lighting. The image, along with the suggested identification, was subsequently sent to the first author for verification. The habitat of the collection site resembles that of an older park, featuring pines (*Pinus* spp., *Picea* spp.), mature *Betula pendula*, fruit trees, and shrubs, among other vegetation. The neighbouring gardens have orchards and larger grassed areas. That evening, the following moth species also flew to light (the list is not exhaustive): *Camptogramma bilineata*, *Idaea seriata*, *Peribatodes rhomboidaria*, *Timandra comae*, *Agrotis segetum*, *Autographa gamma*, *Hadula trifolii*, *Ponomotia candefacta*, *Thalpophila matura*, *Tyta luctuosa*.

The potential occurrence of *Loryma egregialis* larvae is likely to be associated with on-site nesting of the following bird species: *Aegithalos caudatus*, *Chloris chloris*, *Columba palumbus*, *Curruca curruca*, *Dendrocopos syriacus*, *Erithacus rubecula*, *Fringilla coelebs*, *Parus major*, *Passer montanus*, *Phoenicurus ochruros*, *Serinus serinus*, *Streptopelia turtur*, *Sylvia atricapilla*, *Turdus merula*, *Turdus philomelos*.

This paper provides a comprehensive description of the species' diagnosis, male genitalia, bionomics, and geographical distribution. It concludes that *Loryma egregialis* represents a new species record for Central Europe and Hungary.

Results

Loryma Walker, 1859

= *Beria* Walker, 1863

= *Tauba* Walker, 1866

= *Ulotrichodes* Ragonot, 1891

The genus has more than 20 known species in the world. See the following page:

<https://globiz.pyraloidea.org/Pages/Reports/TaxonReport.aspx>

Loryma egregialis (Herrich-Schäffer, 1838)

Locus typicus: Sicily.

Aglossa egregialis Herrich-Schäffer, 1838 (in the original description)

Ulotricha egregialis (Herrich-Schäffer, 1838) [after in Karsholt & Razowski (1996)]

New data. Hungary, Dunaújváros (46.972556, 18.913546), 28–29.08.2024. photo: S. Farkas.

Diagnosis. According to Spuler (1910): The forewing length ranges from 9 to 11 mm. The root and central areas of the forewings exhibit a blackish-brown coloration with a white transverse line and anterior margin dots. The margin field, which is denticulate in the fold, is creamy white. The hindwings are white, as are the first three segments of the blackish abdomen.

Male genitalia. The valva is broad and symmetrical, with a rounded apex and a slightly ventrally convex medial section. The sacculus is V-shaped, and the gnathos is robust, featuring a pointed and recurved apex. The aedeagus is elongated at the base, narrow, and widens medially, with a pointed cornutus that is visible.

Bionomy. The grey, black-spotted larva has been documented inhabiting avian nests, where it resides within a silk gallery and subsists on organic detritus. It is conjectural to propose that the larvae may exhibit a life history similar to that of *Tinea pellionella* Linnaeus, 1758, which is known to inhabit the nests of various *Columba* species as well as poultry houses, and there it feeds on bird feathers. Our understanding of its life cycle remains limited. An old description by Füge (1912) provides a wealth of information. The adults have been observed in a variety of habitats from April to October, bivoltine species, including olive groves, arid, scrubby mountain

Figs 1–2. (1) *Loryma egregialis*, adult: Hungary, Dunaújváros (46.972556, 18.913546), 28–29.08.2024. (2) *L. egregialis*, adult of a prepared specimen: from Turkey (photo: https://lepiforum.org/wiki/page/Loryma_egregialis#/image/2/1)

Fig. 3. Diagnostic characters (indicated) of male genitalia of *Loryma egregialis* (Canary Islands)

(https://lepiforum.org/wiki/page/Loryma_egregialis#/image/4/1 – with minor modifications)

valleys, urban gardens, and areas near cattle and horse stables. Specimens have been collected exclusively through light trapping, suggesting that the imago likely conceals itself during daylight hours.

The new Hungarian observation site and its wider area can be described as non-native deciduous forest and plantations mixed with native trees, uncharacteristic dry grasslands, scattered native or narrow tree lines, dry and semi-dry pioneer scrub, Scots and black pine plantations and spontaneous stands of non-native trees.

Geographical distribution. The known distribution of *Loryma egregialis* essentially covers the Mediterranean region (nearly 400 monitoring points recorded), including Portugal, Spain (including the Canary Islands and the Balearic Islands), France, Italy, North Macedonia, Greece, Bulgaria, Turkey, and Algeria. It has been observed in England and now in Hungary. No records from Belgium (W. de Prins, pers. comm., August 2022). It has also been found in eastern Africa, Southeast Asia, Sumatra and the northern coast of Australia.

In the old literature, Spuler (1910) wrote only: "...In südf frankreich, Sicilien, Giechenland (und Syrien); im Mai. Die Raupe ist unbekannt." In his 2006 European book, Slamka provided very little data about the species. According to him, it inhabits dry and open habitats, and its larval stage is unknown. It is possible that he did not read Füge's 1912 publication, as this study is missing from the book's bibliography.

Discussion. The presence of the species in Hungary can only be conjectured. It is plausible that a breeding bird species may have transported the eggs of *Loryma egregialis* imago within its plumage, allowing the larvae to develop within the nest. The emerged imago has been identified in Hungary. However, it is highly unlikely that the species can endure the winter months of the dominant continent in any developmental stage. Thus, its local occurrence is likely incidental.

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Fig. 4. Location of the *Loryma egregialis* monitoring site in Hungary (black dot).
View of the observation site garden with the collection sheet.
Photo taken in early April 2025 (bottom picture).

Fig. 5. Geographic distribution of *Loryma egregialis* sites in the Europe, Middle East and North Africa (outline map)

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(Note: List of studies used and read during the writing of the manuscript)

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